

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of
accessible IT systems and tools

PROJECT

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools

AGREEMENT NUMBER

LC-01624438/101018048

Report: Makerspace data overview in LIVE IT

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Document Filename	Makerspace data overview in LIVE IT
Nature Of Document	R
Number Of Pages	31
Work Package	All Work Packages
Partner Responsible	All partners
Author(s)	All partners
Contributor(s)	All partners
Reviewed by	Joe Cullen
Approved by	Panagiotis Bamidis, Project Coordinator

PROJECT FULL TITLE	Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools
Start Of Project	1 April 2021
Duration	12 months
Project URL	https://liveit-project.eu/
Disclaimer	The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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Acknowledgements

The LIVE IT team would like to thank all of our collaborating partners, especially those organisations working with us on the ground in developing the Co-Labs, and all of the LIVE IT ‘users’ – people with cognitive disabilities – for giving their time and insights to contribute to this research.

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1 LIVE IT MAKERSPACE REPORT: DATA OVERVIEW

Cognitive walkthrough data

Summary of cognitive walkthrough data

To inform the decision on which community platform to progress with, a prototype platform was set up for both shortlisted platforms (Circle and Mighty Networks), and two users from the UK co-labs were asked to participate in a short cognitive walkthrough of the prototypes to flag usability issues. Users were asked to carry out two tasks:

- Task 1: Sign up to the platform
- Task 2: Navigate through the site and post a comment

User profile information and walkthrough data are shown below in Tables 1,2,3 and 4. In summary, the main findings from the cognitive walkthroughs of both platforms were:

- **Setting up profiles and logging in:** Both users found MN and Circle.so easy for setting up their profiles and could log in without issue
- **Posting comments:** Both users could post comments without problems.
- **Navigating the site:** P1 had few problems in navigating both sites. P2 flagged some accessibility concerns with Mighty Networks in regard to site navigation. They became frustrated that when clicking on a post it opened up in a pop-up window which covered some of the page. They also found it difficult to understand where they were in the site due to lack of sidebar navigation of topics and subtopics.

Whilst both platforms presented some accessibility issues, the Mighty Networks platform presented more issues with site navigation which were thought to be a potential barrier to a greater number of users with CD. Therefore, Circle.so was chosen for the Makerspace platform.

1.1. Circle.so walkthroughs

1.1.1. Participant 1 (Circle)

DATE: 06/12/21	Questions		
<p><i>User details:</i> Female, age range: 25-34 ADHD diagnosis</p>	<p><i>Does the user notice that the correct action is available? Do they know what to do at this step?</i></p>	<p><i>Based on the system's response, does the user know that they did the right thing? Does the user see that progress is being made toward the solution of the task?</i></p>	<p>Notes</p>
Task 1: Sign up to platform			
<p><i>1. Locate and click sign-up button</i></p>	<p>The site uses a bright blue button for signing up. The user doesn't immediately locate it and hovers the mouse over the sidebar scrolling down. After looking through the sidebar, without prompting, the user manages to find it after less than a minute.</p>	<p>After clicking the button, it changes to a lighter blue colour and the sign-up screen appears offering a choice to sign up with email, Twitter or Facebook. The user knows the action is correct and moving towards goal.</p>	<p><i>The initial sign-up button is quite small - might be an issue for users with VI</i></p>
<p><i>2. Locate sign-up with email button</i></p>	<p>There are three buttons (email/twitter/fb). The sign-up with email button is located at the top, uses large text and is bright blue. The user locates the correct button straight away and clicks it.</p>	<p>Yes, the sign-up details page appears with input boxes for user details. Clear progress is being made.</p>	<p><i>The sign-up page asks for full name and at this point, P1 voices concern about inputting name - doesn't like using full name - might be off-putting for some other users too?</i></p>
<p><i>3. Enter the username in the name field</i></p>	<p>The name input box is at the top of the page, the user sees it but has some misgivings as it asks for 'full name'. The user inputs only their first name</p>	<p>Yes, name text input from user keyboard appears onscreen</p>	
<p><i>4. Enter email address in the email address field</i></p>	<p>Yes, the email input box is located underneath and clearly identifiable. The user inputs their email address without issue.</p>	<p>Yes, email address text from user keyboard appears onscreen</p>	

5. Enter password in the password field	The password input box is located underneath email input and clearly identifiable. The user spends a bit of time thinking about a password and inputs it.	Yes, password appears (concealed)	
6. Check terms of service checkbox	The term of service is smaller, but the user locates the checkbox and clicks on it	Not at this point	
7. Locate and click sign-up button	The sign-up button is located under the text input boxes. It's a big blue button, the user locates it easily	After clicking the sign-up button, the profile setup page appears.	
8. Any additional steps	No additional steps	N/A	
Task 2: Navigate through spaces			
1. View welcome information	User could easily view welcome and project info. They suggested that each bullet point should link to a page where these actions could be performed (e.g., link to events page and connect with other members)	N/A	
2. Navigate to 'Emergencies' space	The user noticed that the spaces were listed in the sidebar on the LHS of the screen and was able to locate the 'Emergencies' header easily.	When the user clicked on the emergencies tab, the emergencies page appeared. The user realised the action was correct and progress made.	
3. Find another space (choose one other)	The user located the headings for the other spaces in the sidebar on the LHS without issue. They selected the 'Life Skills' heading.	As with the Emergencies section, when the user clicked on the Life Skills heading, the correct page appeared. The user realised the action was correct and progress made.	
4. Locate comment button	The user located the comment button without issue.	The user clicked on the comment button, and they were directed to the comment input section below the post which says, ' <i>what are your thoughts?</i> '	

5. Enter and post a comment	The user typed in a comment, they located the blue 'post' button underneath, and posted a comment	On click, the 'post' button changed to 'posting' before the comment appeared. The user saw their comment underneath the post.	
6. Any additional steps	The user wanted to delete their comment and was unsure of how to do this. They could see reply and like buttons underneath their comment but not how to edit or delete their comment	With researcher prompting the user found the three dots to the side of the comment and found 'delete comment' option. On selecting this option, a dialogue box appeared asking the user if they were sure they wanted to delete the comment. The user selected the red 'delete' button and the comment was deleted.	<i>Is there any way to make editing and deleting options more obvious, e.g., with an icon (bin)?</i>

Table 1: Participant data for cognitive walkthrough of the Circle.so platform (P1)

1.1.2 Participant 2 (Circle)

DATE: 08/12/21	Questions		
<i>User details: Male, age range: 35 - 49 ASD and ADHD diagnoses</i>	<i>Does the user notice that the correct action is available? Do they know what to do at this step?</i>	<i>Based on the system's response, does the user know that they did the right thing? Does the user see that progress is being made toward the solution of the task?</i>	Notes
Task 1: Sign up to platform			
1. Locate and click sign-up button	The site uses a bright blue button for signing up. The user finds the sign-up button straight away at the top RHS of the screen.	Yes, the user sees the sign-up screen appear and moves to select next button.	
2. Locate sign-up with email button	The user easily identifies the blue sign-up with email button and clicks it immediately.	Yes, the sign-up screen appears	
3. Enter the username in the name field	Yes, they see the data input box and write full name	No response from the system, users move on to email input	

4. Enter email address in the email address field	Yes, the email input box is located underneath and clearly identifiable. The user inputs their email address without issue.	Yes, email address text from user keyboard appears onscreen	
5. Enter password in the password field	User is confused that it doesn't ask them to confirm their password and expresses concern that they input the right password and will remember it correctly.	There is also no option to show password, so user is worried if they have written the correct password. User re-inputs password twice for peace of mind.	Might be difficult for some PwCD as logins and passwords are a known issue
6. Check terms of service checkbox	No, the user doesn't see the terms of service checkbox and clicks the sign-up button	No indication to the user at this point that terms of service has not been checked	
7. Locate and click sign-up button	The user locates the button and presses it without issue.	System response throws up a couple of errors for the user - both problems are identified in red by the system to alert the user. 1. It shows that there is a problem with the password (need to include uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers and symbols); 2. terms and conditions - red writing indicates the user needs to tick the checkbox. The user struggles with password requirements but once they input a password which meets requirements the red writing disappears, and the sign-up button goes back to blue	Password seems to be a bit of an issue as the user can't see what they've input - especially a problem when there are multiple requirements (i.e. both lower and uppercase letters, numbers and symbols in this case)
8. Any additional steps	The site then asks the user to find traffic light images and bicycle images, which they are able to do but become frustrated when there are two pages of images to verify	After clicking through, the verification the profile setup page appeared.	
Task 2: Navigate through spaces			
1. View welcome information	User could view welcome information and reported that it was clear and easy to read.	N/A	

2. <i>Navigate to 'Emergencies' space</i>	The user noticed that the spaces were listed in the sidebar on the LHS of the screen and was able to locate the 'Emergencies' header easily. User commented that they liked the use of icons but could be bigger (see notes)	When the user clicked on the emergencies tab, the emergencies page appeared. The user realised the action was correct and progress made.	User commented that the use of icons for each space header was a good idea, although they were a bit small. Also didn't like the emergency (SOS) icon, suggested alternative
3. <i>Find another space (choose one other)</i>	The user located the headings for the other spaces in the sidebar on the LHS without issue. They selected the 'Self Development' heading.	As with the Emergencies section, when the user clicked on the Self Development heading, the correct page appeared. The user realised the action was correct and progress made.	
4. <i>Locate comment button</i>	User initially didn't see where to post a comment, but then scrolled down and pressed the comment button.	A comment box appeared, and the user was able to input text	User mentioned the icon for comment and like are similar to Facebook and other social media so easy to identify
5. <i>Enter and post a comment</i>	The user typed in a comment, they located the blue 'post' button underneath, and posted a comment	On click, the 'post' button changed to 'posting' before the comment appeared. The user saw their comment underneath the post.	User commented that they liked the use of blue buttons as they were able to identify possible actions easily
6. <i>Any additional steps</i>	No additional steps	N/A	

Table 2: Participant data for cognitive walkthrough of the Circle.so platform (P2)

1.2 Mighty Networks walkthroughs

1.2.1 Participant 1 (MN)

DATE: 06/12/2021	Questions		
<p>User details: Female, age range: 25-34 ADHD diagnosis</p>	<p>Does the user notice that the correct action is available? Do they know what to do at this step?</p>	<p>Based on the system's response, does the user know that they did the right thing? Does the user see that progress is being made toward the solution of the task?</p>	<p>Notes</p>
Task 1: Sign up to platform			
<p>1. Locate and click "Create Account" button</p>	<p>The user locates the purple 'create account' text underneath the sign-in page and pressed it</p>	<p>On click, a user details window appears with sign up information</p>	
<p>2. Enter the name in the first and last name field</p>	<p>User did not want to input full name but was able to locate and input name info easily</p>	<p>On clicking the name field, a purple stroke appears around the input field to highlight the action so user is aware of progress being made</p>	
<p>3. Enter email address in the email address field</p>	<p>Yes, the email input box is located underneath and clearly identifiable. The user inputs their email address without issue.</p>	<p>Yes, email address text from user keyboard appears onscreen</p>	
<p>4. Enter password in the password field</p>	<p>The password input box is located underneath email input and clearly identifiable. The user inputs a password without issue.</p>	<p>On clicking the password field, a purple stroke appears around it</p>	
<p>5. Check terms of service checkbox</p>	<p>On clicking sign up, a pop up appears with terms of service, the user checks the box and presses continue</p>	<p>A profile photo pop-up appears</p>	
<p>6. Any additional steps</p>	<p>The user chooses not to upload a profile image and locates the skip step button</p>	<p>N/A</p>	
Task 2: Navigate through spaces			

1. View welcome information	User couldn't easily find the welcome information (located in the About section). With prompting they found the About section in the sidebar	When the user clicked on the About button a page appears on the RHS with information about the project.	The user didn't like scrolling down in a new page to find the welcome information. It also wasn't immediately obvious to them to go to the sidebar to find info about the project - they would prefer to have welcome info on login
2. Find 'Topics' section	The user noticed a header for topics in the sidebar on the LHS of the screen and was able to click on it without issue.	When the user clicked on the topics tab, the list of topics appeared in the main page.	
3. Navigate to 'Emergencies' topic	User clicked on the Emergencies topic without issue	When the user clicked on the Emergencies tab, the Emergencies page loaded without issue	
4. Find another topic (choose one other)	From the Emergencies topic, the user clicked the back arrow on their browser which returned them to the Topics page. They selected Help and Support from the list	When the user clicked on the Help and Support tab, the page loaded without issue	User commented that they couldn't see the list of topics like in Circle, so used the back arrow to return to the topics list.
5. Locate comment box	The user located the comment box beneath the post.	The user clicked on the comment box which said, 'Share what's on your mind.'	
6. Enter and post a comment	The user typed in a comment, they located the grey 'post' button underneath, and posted a comment	On click, the 'post' button changed to black before the comment appeared. The user saw their comment underneath the post.	
7. Any additional steps	No additional steps	N/A	

Table 3: Participant data for cognitive walkthrough of the Mighty Networks platform (P1)

1.2.2 Participant 2 (MN)

DATE: 08/12/21	Questions		
<p><i>User details:</i> Male, age range: 35 - 49 ASD and ADHD diagnoses</p>	<p>Does the user notice that the correct action is available? Do they know what to do at this step?</p>	<p>Based on the system's response, does the user know that they did the right thing? Does the user see that progress is being made toward the solution of the task?</p>	<p>Notes</p>
Task 1: Sign up to platform			
<p>1. Locate and click "Create Account" button</p>	<p>The user struggles to find the 'create account' text but locates it with help from the researcher.</p>	<p>On click, a user details window appears with sign up information</p>	
<p>2. Enter the name in the first and last name field</p>	<p>The user sees the data input box and inputs their name</p>	<p>On clicking the name field, a purple stroke appears around the input field to highlight the action so user is aware of progress being made</p>	
<p>3. Enter email address in the email address field</p>	<p>Yes, the email input box is located underneath and clearly identifiable. The user inputs their email address without issue.</p>	<p>Yes, email address text from user keyboard appears onscreen</p>	
<p>4. Enter password in the password field</p>	<p>The password input box is located underneath email input and clearly identifiable. The user can see there is an icon with an eye with a cross through it, they click it to make their password visible and input a password without issue.</p>	<p>On clicking the eye icon, the user was able to see their password</p>	<p>The user was happier signing up because of password visibility</p>
<p>5. Check terms of service checkbox</p>	<p>On clicking sign up, a pop up appears with terms of service, the user checks the box and presses continue</p>	<p>A profile photo pop-up appears</p>	
<p>6. Any additional steps</p>	<p>The user chooses not to upload a profile image and locates the skip step button</p>	<p>N/A</p>	
Task 2: Navigate through spaces			

1. View welcome information	User really struggled to find the welcome information (located in the About section). With prompting they found the About section in the sidebar	When the user clicked on the About button a page appears on the RHS with information about the project and the user had to scroll down to find the welcome info.	Similar to P1, this user also found it difficult to find the welcome information and didn't like the layout
2. Find 'Topics' section	The user noticed a header for topics in the sidebar on the LHS of the screen and was able to click on it without issue.	When the user clicked on the topics tab, the list of topics appeared in the main page.	
3. Navigate to 'Emergencies' topic	User clicked on the Emergencies topic without issue	When the user clicked on the Emergencies tab, the Emergencies page loaded but the page appeared as a pop-up on the LHS, instead of loading a new page. User was frustrated viewing the information in this way	User felt that the pop-up was confusing and made the page cluttered as you can still see the rest of the site in the background. User became quite annoyed with the site. Researcher noticed that you could expand the page, but perhaps some PwCD would struggle to find this option
4. Find another topic (choose one other)	From the Emergencies topic, the user couldn't immediately see how to navigate to the other topics and became frustrated. Researcher reminded them about the Topics section, and they found it again in the sidebar. From there they were able to navigate to the Life Skills topic.	When the user clicked on the Life Skills tab, the page loaded without issue	User commented that they found the navigation in MN quite difficult and wasn't as user-friendly as Circle.
5. Locate comment box	The user located the comment box beneath the post without issue.	The user clicked on the comment box which said, 'Share what's on your mind' and realised progress made.	
6. Enter and post a comment	The user typed in a comment, they located the grey 'post' button underneath, and posted a comment	On click, the 'post' button changed to black before the comment appeared. The user saw their comment underneath the post.	
7. Any additional steps	No additional steps	N/A	

Table 4: Participant data for cognitive walkthrough of the Mighty Networks platform (P2)

User Survey Data

Summary of user survey data

To evaluate the usability and effectiveness of the Makerspace prototype at the end of the project, a user survey was conducted using Google Forms. Participants were recruited from the Makerspace platform, co-labs, and also from external forums (e.g., Circle.so wider community, ADHD forum).

Participants were asked to complete a short online survey, consisting of the UMUX-Lite questionnaire for usefulness and usability. Question 1 was modified to assess whether the Makerspace was useful in learning more about digital inclusion for cognitive disability. Participants were asked two additional questions about navigation and continuity of use, as well as three open-ended questions about i) what they liked; ii) main challenges and iii) improvements to the Makerspace. Questions 1-4 used a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

A total of 8 participants responded to the user survey (50% female, age range 18-50 years). Response data is shown in Table 5 below. In summary, the main findings from the user survey were:

- **Usefulness:** User ratings were average for usefulness, with 50% of respondents (4/5) and 33% of respondents (3/5) agreeing that the Makerspace met user needs in learning about cognitive disability and digital conclusion (Scale = 1/5 is strongly disagree to 5/5 strongly agree).
- **Usability:** 50% of respondents reported that the Makerspace was easy to use.
- **Navigation:** 67% of respondents reported that the Makerspace was easy to navigate, with 33% of respondents strongly agreeing (5/5).
- **Continued use:** 67% of respondents reported that they would continue to use the Makerspace, with 33% of respondents neither agreeing nor disagreeing (5/5).

- Positive aspects of Makerspace according to participants:** Participants reported that the Makerspace is “clearly laid out” (P1) and “easy to navigate” (P3), with useful and ‘clear’ images and diagrams. One participant reported: *“I like the information about different challenges, especially about mood and cognitive disability, it's interesting”* (P4).
- Challenges:** Challenges encountered by participants included issues with colour contrast *“everything is the same colour (white), could do with some colour and contrast”* (P3), problems with remembering password on account set-up (P4), feeling nervous about creating posts and making comments (P6) and finding out more about what users can do in the Makerspace.
- Suggested improvements:** Suggestions for improvement included adding more contrast, starting more discussion groups, providing better links to relevant resources and providing more disability-specific information (e.g., specific tools for ADHD (P4)), as well as information on how to connect with other participants (e.g., other parents of children with ASD (P6)).

Questions	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
1. The things that you can do on the Makerspace meet my needs in learning more about digital inclusion for cognitive disability	3	4	4	3	2	4	4	3
2. The Makerspace is easy to use	3	4	4	5	5	5	5	4
3. I was able to find my way around the Makerspace easily	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4
4. I would continue to use the Makerspace	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	3

<p>5. What were the main challenges you found in using the Makerspace?</p>	<p>Clear diagrams and easy access</p>	<p>Easy to navigate. Good forum for exchange of ideas.</p>	<p>clearly laid out</p>	<p>I like the information about different challenges, especially about mood and cognitive disability, it's interesting. The navigation is quite clear.</p>	<p>interesting selection of tools, but not sure how they would be useful.</p>	<p>Useful info and images</p>	<p>Clear way to find tools.</p>	<p>none</p>
<p>6. Could you tell us what things you liked about the Makerspace?</p>	<p>None</p>	<p>None</p>	<p>everything is the same colour (white), could do with some contrast with background. Text on left quite small and not very distinct from background, could use buttons</p>	<p>There is a lot of information about the project that I don't understand and doesn't seem relevant to me. Also, when you sign up, you don't enter the password twice and I couldn't see an option to make the password visible, so this could be a problem if I made a mistake inputting my password and don't remember it.</p>	<p>not sure how to meet others in the community, felt nervous about creating my own posts</p>	<p>Finding out what you can do. The groups are confusing, how do I see everything without being added to a group?</p>	<p>Understanding what my journey should be there.</p>	<p>don't know</p>

<i>7. How would you improve it? What else would you like to be able to do?</i>	access more discussion groups	Better links to other relevant resources	add more contrast in background. use buttons for page links. use keywords/ tags for topics	It would be good if there was more stuff about ADHD or disability-specific info, like what tools would be good for ADHD. For example, I often have a lot of browser tabs open at the same time and it slows my computer down so I would be good to see if there's a tool for helping with that.	not really enough info about cognitive disability and digital world, or the problems people face.	More explanation about some of the topics are about, like scenarios. It would be good to meet other parents of children with ASD.	Needs a better onboarding, maybe with an intro video or talking more about each space and how can I contribute. But overall, great start!	not sure
<i>Age range</i>	Prefer not to say	Prefer not to say	36-50	26-35	18-25	26-35	26-35	18-25
<i>Gender identity</i>	Female	Male	Male	Female	Female	Female	Male	Male
<i>How did you find out about the Makerspace?</i>	LIVE IT project member	University	LIVE IT project member	LIVE IT project member	University	LIVE IT project member	Online forum	University
<i>Do you have a cognitive disability (CD)?</i>	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
<i>Cognitive Disability info (if applicable)</i>	Prefer not to say	Prefer not to say	ADHD	ADHD	Autism, Dyscalculia		Prefer not to say	Prefer not to say

Table 5: Participant response data for the Makerspace user survey

2 LIVE IT MAKERSPACE PLATFORM ACCESSIBILITY

The Makerspace is intended as an online community space for the LIVE IT project and the wider cognitive accessibility community, providing a platform for discussion about useful tools and digital solutions for cognitive accessibility problems. Overall, the following changes have been made to improve the accessibility and usability of the Makerspace platform:

- **Language and technical jargon:** Simplifying language and reducing or separating technical jargon from the main site (e.g., LIVE IT project references and information)
- **Site navigation:** For site navigation we have added:
 - Improved site navigation options, including <back> and <next> links on posts
 - Site map image
 - Quick start video tour showing the different spaces of the site and how to navigate around
 - Quick start infographic guide
- **Content and information display:** We have provided more audio, visual, audio-visual and interactive content:
 - Increased use of **icons**, both small images to illustrate concepts, spaces or terms, and standardised accessibility icons (from WC3) to signpost accessibility features in the site
 - Increased use of **images**, including infographics and other images
 - Increased use of **animated gifs**, including technical support how-tos, and animations for relaxation
 - Use of **audio-only content**, e.g., T2S narration of site text
 - Increased use of **audio-visual content**, including an explainer video, quick-start tour and demos/how-tos.
 - Creating more **interactive content**, including interactive polls and feedback options, and an interactive tutorial
- **User-generated content:** Improving accessibility could also be supported through encouraging more user-generated content:
 - **Creating a post:** We've added more info on how to join in on the Makerspace FAQ, and created a dedicated post with an interactive tutorial, video and slideshow on how to start your own post.
 - **Authoring tools:** We've created a new post on content authoring and design and development tools which may be more accessible to PwCD.

2.1 LANGUAGE AND TECHNICAL JARGON

We have made some changes to the language in the welcome page:

- Stating the purpose of the site as 'a space for the cognitive accessibility community' at the outset
- Providing an overview of what users can do in the makerspace, using a bullet-point list with links and icons

- Providing an overview of what users can find in the 'Start Here' section itself, using a bullet-point list with links
- Limiting references to LIVE IT in the main spaces and creating a new dedicated space for project information. It is hoped that this will help with the sustainability of the Makerspace in having a role beyond the LIVE IT project.

Additionally, throughout the site we have included more signposting, including:

- Providing an overview of what users can find in the spaces, using a bullet-point lists with links
- Reducing technical jargon in other posts

2.2 SITE LAYOUT AND NAVIGATION

Improved structure and navigations options

Changes to the community structure and layout include:

- Welcome posts for each different space provide an overview of what users can find there, with lists and clickable links and icons for better navigation.
- Most useful posts for each space can also pinned in the RHS sidebars, so that they are easier to find.
- As with the welcome and FAQ, filtering project information and references to a dedicated LIVE IT project space, rather than having both Makerspace and LIVE IT content running concurrently.
- Signposting and navigation options at the top and bottom of each post, so that users can more clearly situate themselves and move between pages (See Figure 18).

Figure 18: Navigation options at the top of a post to improve site orientation

[Quick Start Guide: Video tour](#)

Some survey feedback that users need a better idea of what users can find on the Makerspace site and how to navigate through the spaces. To overcome some of the challenges users might encounter with navigation on the site, we've created a Quick Start video guide tour providing an overview of layout of the community, the different spaces and areas (including the discussion area) and how users can contribute to the Makerspace. This Quick Start guide is also supported by an infographic and is located in the Start Here section as a pinned post in the sidebar (See Figure 19).

Figure 19: Opening slide from the quick start guide video with Makerspace walkthrough

Quick Start Guide: Infographic

We've created a Quick Start Guide infographic with links and a QR code to the main site. Once navigating to the Makerspace site, this should help users get a quick impression of the main spaces and what they can do in the community. The infographic is included in the Start Here space Quick Start Guide post, and is also provided in audio format. This guide could also be sent as a leaflet in invitations for other users to join.

Figure 20: Quick Start guide infographic with images and links to support new users in signing up and navigating the community spaces

2.3 CONTENT AND INFORMATION DISPLAY

Much of the Makerspace content has been updated with additional audio, visual, audio-visual and interactive content. Table 1 shows examples of the additional content in alternative display formats:

Content	Type of content	Where located
Makerspace explainer intro	Video	Embedded on Welcome page
Quick start guide infographic	Infographic	Start Here space
Quick start guide video tour	Video	Start Here space
Sitemap with links	Image	Start Here space
Interactive tutorial on how to create a post	Tutorial, video, slideshow and pdf	Discussion space, pinned post
Text-to-speech narration	Audio	Welcome page, FAQ pages
Breathing animation	Animated GIF	Overwhelm page, Challenges
Send a direct message how-to	Animated GIF	FAQ, Communicating with Others
Authoring tools overview	Infographic	DevSpace
Accessibility issue chatbot feedback	Interactive feedback form	FAQ page

Table 1: Examples of additional Makerspace content using alternative display formats

Increased use of icons

We've increased the use of icons in existing posts, including more small icons and emojis to illustrate concepts, spaces or terms (e.g., Figure 22). We've also introduced the use of standardised accessibility icons (from WC3) to signpost accessibility features in the site, particularly the use of new audio features (e.g., Figure 9).

Increased use of images and infographics

We've increased the use of images in existing posts to illustrate concepts and themes. We've also created several infographics to explain some of the ideas and processes described in text format, for example in the Makerspace FAQ Code of Conduct, and Communicating with Others sections. See Figures 21 and 22 for changes made to the code of conduct page.

Figure 21: Code of conduct original page with no images or icons

Figure 22: Updated code of conduct page with infographic and icons

Figure 23: Updated communication page with infographic

Use of animated gifs

We've added some animated gifs (although limited this so as to avoid the content being too busy, distracting or overwhelming). Examples include a shape visualisation to support breathing and reduce anxiety on the 'Overwhelm' page (see Figure 25), and how-to illustrations in the FAQ section (See Figure 24).

The main Circle.so site uses animated gifs to support user how-tos. We have embedded some of these gifs in the Makerspace FAQ section, for example the gif below which shows users how to send a direct message.

Figure 24: Animation showing users how to send a direct message (DM) to other users

Some things to try

1. Breathing

Breathing in time with this animated gif can help you breathe more deeply and start to reduce feelings of anxiety and overwhelm. Try and do this for at least a few minutes to feel an effect:

[This is a viral animation sourced from [Giphy](#)]

Figure 25: Updated 'Overwhelm' page with breathing animation

Embedding audio

With no native Text-to-Speech function in Circle.so (to our knowledge this is not a native or embedded feature in any online community platforms), we explored other options for building audio content into the site. Initially, a simple solution didn't seem possible:

- Attaching an audio file is possible but it won't play in the platform, the user has to download and play the audio, which could be off-putting to many users.
- Audio embed options include uploading a file to Soundcloud and embedding the link in Circle. However, this embeds a large Soundcloud audio player which takes up a lot of space in the browser and could be distracting.
- Using video embed apps (e.g., VideoAsk), or screen capture software (e.g., Loom) to support audio content, but this also distracting and not a simple approach.

Eventually we found a workaround in changing the audio file format (e.g., from WAV) to mp3 allows it to play natively in a post and provides a simple player which is easy to control (See. Figure 26).

This feature has enabled Text-to-Speech translation of much of the site's text content in the Start Here area, with FAQs now available in audio playback. To signpost this, we've used icons and text to provide instructions on how to hear narrated content (see Figure 26).

Figure 26: Text-to-speech narration of Makerspace welcome text, with audio icons (including WC3) for signposting.

Audio-visual content

More video content has been added to the site, including videos in tool spotlight posts, demos, how-tos and an explainer video.

Introductory 'explainer' video

It was clear from the survey feedback that users need a better idea of what the Makerspace is for (e.g., main purpose and goals, target users, and what users can find on the site). To clarify this, we've created an introductory 'explainer' video, providing an overview of the key aims, spaces, and activities users can carry out on the Makerspace. The video is embedded on the Welcome page.

Figure 27: Opening slide from the Makerspace explainer video

Other demos, tours and how-tos have been added to the site, including:

- Quick Start video tour (detailed in the previous section)
- Video on how to create a post in the discussion space.

Interactive content

We've also added more interactive content, including polls, interactive feedback and a step-by-step tutorial. Whilst users are currently able to attach their own audio and video files to posts and comments, we looked at options to provide feedback in posts. Whilst not straightforward, using the VideoAsk app allows this to some extent. E.g., a post about useful accessibility tools has been updated to enable users to provide audio and video feedback to the original video, embedded in the Makerspace site itself (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: VideoAsk app showing options for user feedback via embedded video, audio or text reponse.

Interactive tutorial

Using Iorad software, we've created an Interactive, step-by-step tutorial on how to create a post in the discussion space. This is also available in video format, an audio-visual slideshow and as a downloadable pdf guide with step-by-step instructions.

(Tutorial [Link](#))

Figure 29: Images from the interactive tutorial on how to create a post in the Makerspace Livestreaming / live video chatroom

One of the issues with Circle.so was the delay of the Livestream feature, which we had intended to use for LIVE IT webinars and hackathons. This would have helped to increase the number of users in the community, and also to boost participation levels. However, the Livestream feature was not made available by Circle until the end of the project. Additionally, having originally stated it would be available to all users, it was only made available for premium plans. We explored other options for implementing a live video chatroom/virtual hangout for users to have virtual discussions, but all options are only available with premium plans. The options we looked at include:

- Circle’s own livestream feature (needs a premium plan)
- Mixily embedded live video (needs premium plan for embedding code)
- Zoom integration (not currently available)

2.4 USER-GENERATED CONTENT

Creating a post: We’ve added more info on how to join in on the Makerspace FAQ, and created a dedicated post with an interactive tutorial, video and slideshow on how to start your own post (detailed in the previous section)

Authoring tools: We’ve created a new post on content authoring and design and development tools which may be more accessible to PwCD (See Figure 30).

Figure 30: Infographic on authoring tools

Additional accessibility provision

Report an accessibility issue page

For additional accessibility support, we've added a page for users to report accessibility issues, with a number of ways to do so:

- Sending a direct message to Makerspace support
- Posting a comment on the accessibility issues page so other members can share their experiences and workarounds
- A feedback form to report issues

- **Fill out the chat feedback form here:**

Powered by Typeform

How accessible do you find the Makerspace?

0 → Not at all accessible
5 → Very accessible

0 1 2 3 4 5

- **Fill out the chat feedback form here:**

Powered by Typeform

Please tell us about your accessibility issue:

Skip

Thanks for sharing your feedback with us!

Figure 31: Interactive chatbot-style feedback form for accessibility issues.

Using Typeform, we've added an interactive chatbot-style feedback form for sharing accessibility issues. Many participants in both the lifeworld analysis interviews and co-labs talked about the usefulness of digital assistants, so this feedback form is set up to imitate that.

Provision for screen readers and keyboard-only navigation

Additional accessibility provision is currently limited on the basic plan but could be upgraded to include better accessibility for screen readers and keyboard-only navigation using JavaScript code. A Circle.so user in the wider community has written guidelines and code for improving the accessibility of circle communities in Circle version 2.0 through JavaScript customisation (see [Link in Circle.so](#))